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Ras oncogene expression controls activation of CENP centromere proteins in transformation.

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We studied control of the core components of the cell by a Ras oncogene in human cells using RNA-sequencing. CENPI, CENPJ, CENPQ, CENPX, CENPW, CENPN, CENPB, and CENPO were all strongly activated by G12V in human cells. Oncogenic mutation of Ras is associated with centromere re-organization.